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Adaptive Buckling-Driven Composite Structures for Next Generation Aircraft

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Outline

- Introduction
- NABUCCO project
- Buckling-driven mechanisms for composite adaptive structures
- Concluding remarks

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Future Aircraft Configurations

Do aircraft structures still represent a design challenge?

Aeronautics Vision for Achieving Carbon Neutrality

The European Green Deal, COM (2019) 640

Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda, EU (2020)

Destination 2050, A Route to Net Zero European Aviation, 2021

Design Challenges for Aircraft Structures

Weight reduction is still one of the major drivers

How to get it?

- Advancements on **design tools and processes** (multidisciplinary, validated...)
- Circular economy – modular vehicle architecture and remanufacturing, **greening industry**
- New lightweight and easily recyclable **materials**
- **Relaxation of well-established and historically consolidated design constraints**

“Strategic Transport Research and Innovation Agenda (STRIA) - Vehicle Design and Manufacturing”

Malkin P., **Bisagni C.**, Golinska P., Schmitt D., van den Bossche P., Salvato F.

European Commission, Directorate-General for Research and Innovation, Directorate H - Transport, Unit H.1 - Transport strategy, EUR KI-01-17-930-EN-N, 2017

Buckling of Primary Structures

<https://shellbuckling.com/index.php>
Photograph by Connie Indrebo, Crazy Creek Air Adventures,
Middletown, California

J. Singer, J. Arbocz and T. Weller,
Buckling Experiments, Vol. 1, 1998.

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NABUCCO - A Paradigm Shift for Aerospace Structures

Research funded by **ERC Advanced Grant**
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NABUCCO - *New Adaptive and BUCKling-driven COmposite aerospace structures*

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European Research Council
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Traditional approach

Buckling avoided:

- Stiffness reduction
- Nonlinear response
- Snap-through
- High variability (imperfections)

NABUCCO approach

Buckling exploited:

- Load redistribution
- Shape variation
- Fast response
- Large design space

NABUCCO - A Paradigm Shift for Aerospace Structures

NABUCCO - A Paradigm Shift for Aerospace Structures

- Goal** Develop new concepts of adaptive buckling-driven composite structures for next generation more efficient and sustainable aircraft
- Challenge** Buckling: from phenomenon to be avoided to a design opportunity
- Results** Adaptive structures for aircraft morphing wings

NABUCCO - Methodology

NABUCCO - Building Block Approach

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Buckling-driven Multi-stable Adaptive Structures

Study of **buckling-driven mechanisms** implemented in a composite wing to be used for shape morphing application

3. Feasibility in a wing

- Design parameters
- Experimental validation

2. Implementation in a wing box

- Load case
- Selective stiffness variation
- Shear center modification

1. Buckling-driven mechanisms

- Onset of buckling
- Post-buckling stiffness

Zhang J. and Bisagni C., "Buckling-driven mechanisms for twisting control in adaptive composite wings", *Aerospace Science and Technology*, 118(2021)107006, 2021.

Buckling-driven Mechanisms

Uniaxial-loaded quasi-isotropic plate

- IM7/8552 composite, lay-up $[0/45/-45/90]_s$
- Simply-supported on all edges

First 3 eigenmodes

\tilde{z}_x Mode 1

\tilde{z}_x Mode 2

\tilde{z}_x Mode 3

Point constraint

Area constraint

Maximum displacement constraint

Zhang J. and Bisagni C., "Buckling-driven mechanisms for twisting control in adaptive composite wings", *Aerospace Science and Technology*, 118(2021)107006, 2021.

Buckling-driven Mechanisms

→ Baseline

→ Point constraint

- P_{cr} 12% ↑
- K_{post} -12% ↓

→ Area constraint

- P_{cr} 37% ↑
- K_{post} +19% ↑

→ Max displacement constraint

- K_{post} +102% ↑

Implementation in a Simplified Wing Box

- Rectangular wing box section between two ribs
 - $L / H = 3$
 - Rear spar: $[0/45/-45/90]_s$
 - Front spar, top and bottom skin: $[0/45/-45/90]_{3s}$

Implementation in a Simplified Wing Box

Zhang J. and Bisagni C., "Buckling-driven mechanisms for twisting control in adaptive composite wings", *Aerospace Science and Technology*, 118(2021)107006, 2021.

Implementation in a Simplified Wing Box

Effects of buckling

→ Selective **stiffness variation**

Buckled rear spar

→ **Shear center**

Shifts forward 12%

→ **Stress distribution**

May change the failure mode thus may play a beneficial role in structural design

Zhang J. and Bisagni C., “Buckling-driven mechanisms for twisting control in adaptive composite wings”, *Aerospace Science and Technology*, 118(2021)107006, 2021.

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Concluding Remarks

- The next generation aircraft will require to be **lighter, more flexible and sustainable**, with the same or increased level of safety.
- The relaxation of some of the established design constraints, together with the use of **new lightweight and recyclable materials**, can contribute to the development of new breakthrough technologies and design philosophies.
- Structures able to work in the post-buckling field and able to adapt their shape during flight conditions will act on **two of the biggest levers for the future of clean aviation: reduced weight and increased efficiency**.
- **Advanced modelling and design tools** (multidisciplinary, validated...) are needed to predict the behavior of flexible and sustainable structures, including damage initiation and propagation until final failure.

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Thanks for your attention!

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